

Synthesis and Study of Azatriterpenes

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In order to obtain some biologically interesting compounds, oleanolic acid (1) was oxidised to its keto derivative (2) which was converted into the 2-hydroximino-3-one (3) and then 2,3-dihydroximino derivative (4). Compound 4 on treatment with potassium hydroxide and ethylene glycol gave the furazan derivative (5) and on treatment with sodium hypochlorite in ethanolic sodium hydroxide gave the furoxan derivatives (6).

THE fusion of heterocyclic systems at position-2 and -3 of the steroid nucleus has afforded many clinically useful compounds¹. With a view that the fusion of heterocyclic system to ring-A of triterpenes may give interesting biologically active compounds, we selected oleanolic acid as the starting material and carried out fusion of furazan and furoxan (1,2,5-oxadiazole *N*-oxide) rings to ring-A of the triterpene.

Oleanolic acid (1) was oxidised with Jones' reagent² to give its keto derivative (2) which on treatment with isoamyl nitrite in acidic medium afforded 2-hydroximino-3-one (3) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

3 showed uv absorption maximum at 240 nm and the maximum shifted to 292 nm in alkaline medium. The ketoxime (3) was converted to the 2,3-hydroximino compound (4) by oximation with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine and it exhibited uv absorption maximum at 222 nm. The bathochromic shift of ultraviolet absorption maximum to 279 nm indicated the presence of antiform of the dioxime. The dioximino derivative (4) was cyclised to furazan (5) in basic medium. It showed a uv absorption maximum at 219 nm. Interestingly, in the nmr spectrum different methyl group signals got separated, which may be due to the fusion of heterocyclic ring system in ring-A (Table 1). With

TABLE 1—NMR SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	δ value for methyl signals*
Oleanolic acid acetate	0.77, 0.90, 0.98, 1.15 (Total protons 21)
Oleanolic acid (1)	0.82, 0.92, 1.03, 1.18 (Total protons 21)
2-Hydroximino-3-oxo-oleanolic acid (3)	0.80, 0.93, 1.17 (Total protons 21)
2,3-Dioximino-oleanolic acid (4)	0.97 (broad), 1.25 (broad)
[2,3-c]Furazan of oleanolic acid (5)	0.88 (6H), 0.95 (3H), 0.98 (3H), 1.21 (3H), 1.35 (3H), 1.45 (3H)
[2,3-c]Furoxan of oleanolic acid (6) ^a	0.97 (6H), 1.02 (3H), 1.28 (3H), 1.37 (3H), 1.42 (3H), 1.47 (3H)
[2,3-c]Furoxan of oleanolic acid (6) ^b	0.82 (3H), 0.93 (6H), 0.95 (3H), 1.15 (3H), 1.32 (3H), 1.42 (3H)

*All singlets. ^aM.p. 312–15°, ^bM.p. 184–87°.

sodium hypochlorite, the dioximino compound (4) afforded furoxans (6). On fractional crystallisation of 6, two compounds (m.p. 312–15° and 184–87°) were obtained and both showed uv maxima at 256 nm. The signals for methyl groups in the nmr spectra of both the compounds got resolved as in the case of furazan (5) (Table 1).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Hitachi-200 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian Em-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an

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internal standard. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

Oleanolic acid 3-one (2): To a stirred solution of oleanolic acid (0.6 g) dissolved in aldehyde-free acetone (15 ml), was added Jones reagent till the colour of the reagent persisted at 20°. The reaction mixture was poured into water and the resulting solid was extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed, dried and processed as usual to afford **2** (0.5 g), m.p. 183–85°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 855, 1 705, 1 585, 1 380, 1 280 and 1 020 cm^{-1} .

2-Hydroximino-3-oxo-oleanolic acid (3): Concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.25 ml) was added to a well-stirred solution of **2** (0.35 g) in benzene (5 ml) and methanol (0.5 ml). Isoamyl nitrite (0.2 ml) in benzene (0.5 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 15 min and the solution was further stirred for 2 h. It was then poured into water and the resulting solid was extracted with ether, the organic layer washed, dried and processed in usual manner to give **3** (0.32 g), m.p. 222–25°; λ_{\max} (MEOH) 240 and (alkaline MEOH) 292 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 080, 2 855, 1 705, 1 460, 1 390 and 1 275 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 0.80, 0.93, 1.17, 1.25 (all singlets integrating for 21H) and 5.37 (1H, t, 12-CH).

2,3-Dioximino oleanolic acid (4): To a solution of **3** (0.2 g) in pyridine (5 ml), was added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.4 g) and the reaction mixture was heated at 100° for 3 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water till free from pyridine, dried and crystallised from acetone–n-hexane to give **4** (0.3 g), m.p. 208–12° (Found: C, 72.03; H, 9.28; N, 5.88. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 72.25; H, 9.3; N, 5.6%); λ_{\max} (MEOH) 222 (log ϵ 3.71) and (alkaline MEOH) 279 nm (log ϵ 3.88); ν_{\max} 3 145, 2 855, 1 705, 1 450, 1 385 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) 0.97 (broad), 1.25 (broad) (both integrating for 21H) and 5.37 (1H, t, 12-CH).

[2,3-c]Furazan of oleanolic acid (5): A suspension of **4** (0.2 g) and potassium hydroxide (0.2 g) in ethylene glycol (5 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h during which the reactants dissolved. The cooled reaction mixture was then poured into water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was washed, dried and crystallised from methanol to give **5** (0.15 g), m.p. 242–44° (Found: C, 75.36; H, 9.46; N, 5.12. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_2\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 74.96; H, 9.23; N, 5.83%); λ_{\max} (MEOH) 219 nm (log

ϵ 3.66); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 855, 1 705, 1 455, 1 375, 1 200, 1 170 and 890 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 0.88 (6H, s), 0.95 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.21 (3H, s), 1.35 (3H, s), 1.45 (3H, s) and 5.37 (1H, t, 12-CH).

[2,3-c]Furoxan of oleanolic acid (6a, b): Compound **4** (0.2 g) was dissolved in a mixture of ethanol and sodium hydroxide (20%), was treated with sodium hypochlorite solution and left overnight. It was then poured into ice-cold water (100 ml), filtered, dried and on fractional crystallisation with methanol afforded a compound in the first crop (80 mg), m.p. 312–15° (Found: C, 72.17; H, 8.46; N, 5.15. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 72.54; H, 8.93; N, 5.64%); λ_{\max} (MEOH) 256 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 840, 1 620, 1 460, 1 140 and 935 cm^{-1} ; δ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO}-d_6$) 0.97 (6H, s), 1.02 (3H, s), 1.28 (3H, s), 1.37 (3H, s), 1.42 (3H, s), 1.47 (3H, s) and 5.40 (1H, b, 12-CH).

The mother liquor on further concentration gave another compound (40 mg), m.p. 184–87° (Found: C, 72.13; H, 8.41; N, 5.21. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 72.54; H, 8.93; N, 5.64%); λ_{\max} (MEOH) 256 nm; δ (CDCl_3) 0.82 (3H, s), 0.93 (6H, s), 0.95 (3H, s), 1.15 (3H, s), 1.32 (3H, s), 1.42 (3H, s) and 5.40 (1H, b, 12-CH).

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